

Authentic Leadership in Sales Management: The Effects on Salespeople's Task Related Outcomes

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Abstract

Authentic leadership, as a new leadership concept emerging from the demand for honest and reliable leaders, has attracted the attention of the business community. The relationship between authentic leaders and their followers is being investigated across many disciplines. This study focuses on authentic leadership in sales management and explores how it affects the task-related outcomes of salespeople, such as learning orientation, customer orientation, intrinsic motivation and working hard. The data for the study were obtained from 364 salespeople and analysed using the partial least squares method. The results indicate that authentic leadership has significant positive effects upon learning orientation ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$), customer orientation ($\beta=0.358$; $p<0.01$), intrinsic motivation ($\beta=0.334$; $p<0.01$), and working hard ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$). As the theory suggests that authentic leadership makes important contributions to the development of followers, this study is the first to explore these contributions upon salespeople's activities that they undertake within their sales tasks and leads to success in personal selling. Findings indicate that authentic leadership has significant positive effects upon salespeople's individual task related outcomes.

Keywords: Authentic leadership, Learning orientation, customer orientation, Intrinsic motivation, Hard-working

1. Introduction

Customers often have doubts regarding how reliable salespeople are at their tasks, even if sales organizations have developed so much over time. Many people have concerns that salespeople push them to close the sales without providing accurate information or being honest about the facts. It is obvious that building customer trust is one of the first requirements for long-term sales success. However, the pressure exerted by salespeople instead leads to short-term results at the expense of success in the longer term. Salespeople are not alone in being accused of taking such an approach; sales supervisors, who deeply feel the pressure of reaching sales goals, may encourage their teams to adopt a pressured approach and, occasionally, to ignore the importance of ethical behaviour. Such a culture within sales may lead to negative consequences and even the loss of some customers forever. The extent to which customers are misled during the various stages of purchase will likely be noticed in phases such as consumption, conversion to other products and services or resell. Where it is noticed, customers will naturally question the reliability of the supplier and maybe this will discourage them from making subsequent purchases. Due to recent developments in communication tools, the damage may not be limited to a single customer.

In such an environment, sales supervisors' leadership characteristics are increasingly important. Authentic leaders, who depend on high moral and ethical standards, respect their followers and appreciate the importance of well-being and a better society, are needed in sales organizations. Since sales supervisors are the ones whom salespeople contact most often, their behaviours and attitudes inevitably shape those of salespeople. It is obvious that sales supervisors play an important role in salespeople's development. Often working alone in the field, salespeople regard their supervisors as not simply a manager. Especially for salespeople who work out of their company's headquarters, their supervisors are the main link between them and the company. In such a scenario, leadership is important, given that a salesperson understands how their performance and behaviours are evaluated by the company with the help of their supervisor's reactions and feedback. In other words, if sales supervisors also become a role model (Chakrabarty et al., 2008), they may influence the behaviours of their staff as well (Shannahan et al., 2012).

Authentic leadership theory suggests that authentic leadership makes important contributions to the development of followers, and their attitudes and behaviours. Avolio et al. (2004) and Jensen & Luthans (2006) have stated that authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's task commitment, job satisfaction and the meaningfulness behind their activities. At the same time, authentic leadership is thought to improve the willingness from staff to make more effort as well as impact positively on absenteeism and intention to leave. Thus, authentic leadership is believed to lead to high performance (Gardner et al., 2005). In their study Walumbwa et al. (2008) have stated that authentic leadership contributes to organizational citizenship behaviours, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Ilies et al. (2005) have further stated that authentic leaders empower their followers by building high quality relationships instead of tangible rewards. According to the theory of social exchange, whenever salespeople feel that they are important, they will increase their effort resulting in greater productivity (Walumbwa et al., 2008). That said, quantitative research that

proves such claims within the sales field remains insufficient.

The main problem to be addressed by this study concerns the effects of authentic leadership upon salespeople's individual task-related outcomes. The activities that salespeople undertake within their sales tasks and leads to success in personal selling, such as learning orientation, customer orientation, intrinsic motivation and being hard-working are considered as individual task outcomes. In many previous studies, these constructs were investigated in the context of sales. Sujan et al. (1994), Kohli et al. (1998), and Silver et al. (2006) have stated that a learning orientation helps salespeople improve their sales performance. On the other hand, Franke & Park (2006), Cross et al. (2007), Wachner et al. (2009), and Schwepker & Good (2012) have stated that it is customer orientation that helps to increase customer satisfaction and customer retention. Furthermore, customer orientation is believed to increase salespeople's creativity (Wang & Miao, 2015). According to Sujan (1986), Weitz et al. (1986), Spiro & Weitz (1990), and Oliver & Anderson (1994), intrinsic motivation is key to sales performance. Besides these, being hard-working is also an indispensable factor for success in sales (Sujan, 1986; Brown & Peterson, 1994; Sujan et al., 1994; VandeWalle et al., 1999; Krishnan et al., 2002). This study focuses on the effects of sales supervisors' authentic leadership behaviours and interactions in inspiring these outcomes. Due to the direct impact of salespeople on firm performance, it's important to understand the factors that motivate salespeople and determine their performance (Hunter & Perreault, 2006). The findings of this study, then, ought to highlight how the effects of authentic leadership are manifest within sales management.

1.1 Authentic Leadership

Leaders who are driven by personal passions may lead their followers towards disasters of their own. At the beginning of this century, the business environment was shaken by numerous scandals. Especially in cases such as Enron and Parmalat, it was found that the main reasons behind the scandals were directly related to defective leadership. The evolution of authentic leadership is a response (May et al., 2003; Cooper et al., 2005), then, to the subsequent demand for leaders who can be trusted. The desire for leaders who are firmly committed to ethical behaviour, flexible towards change, hopeful and optimistic, and who pay attention to the needs of their followers has inspired the conceptualization of authentic leadership (Kinsler, 2014).

The concept of authenticity goes back to ancient times. Authenticity, which is described as "knowing yourself and acting accordingly", was identified in many different cultures throughout history (Gardner et al., 2011). In the modern context, positive psychology literature defines authenticity as recognizing one's own experiences (values, thoughts, emotions, wants, needs, preferences and beliefs), and acting in accordance with them (Harter, 2002, as cited in Luthans & Avolio, 2003). Therefore, authenticity means to act in compliance with real thoughts and beliefs (Avolio & Gardner, 2005; Gardner et al., 2005).

Authentic leadership is a leadership approach in which moral characteristics, internal discipline and positive personal values are highlighted. Authentic leaders are not only task- or people-centric. In a broader sense, they respond to the needs of their followers and even those

of the wider community. They have the highest levels of personal ethical values. They also share these values with their followers and, in the process, create mutual trust between each other. The moral virtue of authentic leaders does not mean that they are infallible, however. On the contrary, authentic leaders consider making mistakes as nothing extraordinary and clearly accept their faults; neither do they seek to avoid taking responsibility when mistakes do happen (Toor & Ofori, 2008).

Self-esteem is also important in authentic leadership. Leaders who understand the positive and negative characteristics they possess and accept them will be stronger psychologically (Kernis, 2003). Being able to be more open and friendly toward other people will enable them to enjoy successful human relations. Ryan and Deci (2000a) have stated that, despite threats or expectations in life, one can still stay faithful to one's own opinions and beliefs. In this way, people whose authenticity exhibit significant physical and psychological aspects will generate more positive results (Ryan & Deci, 2000a, 2000b; Kernis & Goldman, 2006). Furthermore, ethical behaviours and a focus on development are two main issues relevant to authentic leadership. Moral values not only derive from nature; continuous improvement in moral values is also critical to remaining successful in authentic leadership (Walumbwa et al., 2008).

Avolio et al. (2004) defined authentic leaders as "individuals who are deeply aware of how they think and behave, who are perceived by others as being aware of their own and others' values, moral perspectives, knowledge, and strengths, and who are confident, hopeful, optimistic, resilient, and high on moral character". According to Shamir and Eliam (2005), authentic leaders' leadership style is sincere. They do not try to be a leader; instead they simply exhibit their own behaviours. Neither do they deal with other people's expectations, nor try to comply with these expectations. They always behave according to their beliefs. For them, leadership is not about possessing or pursuing status or respectability. Authentic leaders behave in line with their own values; although this does not mean that they are unique and inaccessible. On the contrary, authentic leaders' beliefs, values and goals can be similar to those of their followers.

Some leaders do not need any help to become authentic. In this regard, Mahatma Gandhi and Nelson Mandela epitomized the concept of authentic historical characters. For other leaders, authentic leadership may develop through the intervention of appropriate support (Cooper et al., 2005). Here, another important process is self-regulation, which is a process related to a person's behaviours, assessment of these behaviours upon intrinsic standards and, depending on this review, reinforcement or reduction of the behaviours (Stajkovic & Luthans, 1998). Being concerned with personal behaviour control, self-regulation makes a person check the causes for those wanted or unwanted behaviours, as well as exhibit behaviours that would lead them to avoid unwanted situations (Leroy et al., 2011).

According to Walumbwa et al. (2008), authentic leadership has four dimensions. These are: (1) self-awareness, (2) balanced processing, (3) internalized moral perspective, and (4) relational transparency. Self-awareness concerns the awareness of a leader regarding their own values, motivations and emotions. It helps leaders know the impact of these

characteristics upon their behaviours. In addition, self-awareness involves accepting contradictions found within their own personality. In turn this increases a leader's confidence; it is also important in terms of psychological health (Kernis, 2003). Authentic leaders are aware of their strengths and weaknesses. They recognize this awareness as a source of power, in that they know the limits and depth of their talents (Avolio & Gardner, 2005). For this reason, the risks and the responsibilities they carry are kept at an appropriate level. Authentic leaders are also aware of how their behaviours affect others, as well as how others evaluate their actions. This helps them become successful in social relations.

Balanced processing relates to a leader's self-assessment using objective information; in other words, a leader should observe their behaviours from an independent perspective and avoid exaggerated thoughts about themselves (Kernis, 2003). With the help of balanced processing, a leader can evaluate their strengths and weaknesses objectively. When mistakes occur, many people ignore their own flawed contribution in order to maintain self-esteem. In authentic leadership, there is no place for such indulgence. Moreover, authentic leaders will seek all available information when taking a decision. By placing particular emphasis on being fair, they increase the level of trust that their followers have in them (Ilies et al., 2005).

Internalized moral perspective emphasizes the high moral and ethical standards that are the most important features of an authentic character (Luthans and Avolio, 2003). Authentic leaders avoid misleading behaviours for personal purposes, preferring an honest attitude within both themselves and others. This attitude helps them to inhibit erroneous actions in order to meet the expectations of their followers and please them (Marques, 2010). Internalized moral perspective implies a leader's resistance to the expectations of the social structure they belong to, as well as adhere to their own high moral values. May et al. (2003) have stated that this dimension is very important to leaders' decision-making processes. Accordingly, authentic leaders do not walk away from their own values even if their decisions are unpopular at certain times (Walumbwa et al., 2008).

Finally, relational transparency infers the importance of a leader in conveying clarity and honesty in relations. To this extent, authentic leaders should exhibit behaviours in a transparent manner in the relations they engage in. Authentic leaders do not hide their positive and negative characteristics; rather, they share their thoughts and feelings visibly. Moreover, they encourage people to behave in a similar way. They are open to other people's opinions and respect them (Avolio et al., 2004). Authentic leaders create long-term relationships based on sincerity and trust. While sharing their feelings, however, they also avoid hurting others (Avolio & Gardner, 2005). In this regard, they demonstrate self-discipline. Authentic leaders can help their followers understand their style through these attitudes.

1.2 Learning Orientation

Most of the time, sales supervisors are so busy meeting short-term goals that they may neglect the development of their staff (Sujan et al., 1994). With the belief that learning can yield benefits in the long-term (Garvin, 1993), many of them focus on their teams' productivity, which is a view that is accepted by salespeople as well. In fact, learning is

critical to sustainable success in today's competitive markets (Wang & Netemeyer, 2002). Learning orientation is defined as the willingness by salespeople to put effort into self-development in terms of knowledge and skills (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; VandeWalle et al., 1999; Wang & Netemeyer, 2002).

With an intrinsic aspiration, learning-oriented salespeople consistently try to be better at sales. They regard taking responsibility during difficult tasks or finding new approaches to general processes as opportunities for learning (Sujan et al., 1994). Accordingly, they do not mind making mistakes because failure can offer invaluable knowledge. In turn their courage helps them to adapt to change more easily (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; Ahearne et al., 2010). When faced with challenging tasks, learning-oriented salespeople may suggest creative solutions and implement them successfully (Gong et al., 2009).

Companies, then, ought to facilitate individual learning at the earliest opportunity if they wish to raise organizational learning levels and become more successful in the process (Sinkula et al., 1997; Klimecki & Lassleben, 1998; Calantone et al., 2002). To create a competitive advantage, sales organizations should focus on the development of their sales staff (Kohli et al., 1998; McFarland, 2003). Sujan et al. (1994), Kohli et al. (1998), and Silver et al. (2006) have stated that a learning orientation helps salespeople improve their sales performance.

H₁: Authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's learning orientation.

1.3 Customer Orientation

In terms of sales management, customer orientation is concerned with applying the marketing concept to building relationships with customers (Saxe & Weitz, 1982). In this context, salespeople analyse both targeted customers and their competitors very closely, gathering market information and using it to create a value to customers (Slater & Narver, 1995). As they are interested in the longer term, customer-oriented salespeople not only focus on selling their products, but on nurturing customer relations (Schwepker, 2003). Moreover, salespeople may participate in product development or improvement processes in order to respond customers' expectations. In turn, comprehensive outcomes that go beyond simply selling products are delivered (Schwepker & Good, 2011, 2012).

Customer-oriented salespeople place great importance on the relations they enjoy with customers. In the selling process, they encourage their customers to express their needs and wants clearly. Based on this information, they create proper solutions for their customers as well as stating the 'pros and cons' of each option. They avoid sales pressure and try to make their customers feel comfortable (Saxe and Weitz, 1982). They also consider their company's capacity for meeting the requirements of customers objectively (Pettijohn et al., 2007). By adopting this approach, they are able to foster customer trust (Schwepker, 2003; Bateman & Valentine, 2015) and long-term customer satisfaction (Saxe & Weitz, 1982; Joshi & Randall, 2001).

A significant amount of research has indicated that customer orientation has a positive correlation with sales performance (Franke & Park, 2006; Cross et al., 2007; Wachner et al., 2009; Schwepker & Good, 2012; Mehrabi et al., 2012). Moreover, Rozell et al. (2006) have

stated that customer orientation has helped to increase customer satisfaction and customer retention. It has also been suggested that customer orientation can increase salespeople's creativity (Wang & Miao, 2015), which leads to relationship development (Singh & Koshy, 2011).

H₂: Authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's customer orientation.

1.4 Intrinsic Motivation

The motivation theory help sales supervisors understand why salespeople's efforts vary in specific cases (Walker et al., 1977; Churchill et al., 1985; Anderson & Oliver, 1987). Scholars believe that motivated salespeople put greater effort into their work and gain better sales results (Sujan, 1986; Weitz et al., 1986). Motivation can be discussed from two perspectives in terms of motivational factors. While extrinsic motivation is motivation derived from the tangible benefits provided by the company (e.g., compensation, incentives or additional pay), intrinsic motivation instead emerges from salespeople's individual goals and characteristics (Bassett-Jones & Lloyd, 2005). In other words, intrinsic motivation concerns salespeople's intention behind the sales task rather than any connection to external factors (Leonard et al., 1999).

Intrinsic rewards that are related to individual emotions and feelings are important for intrinsic motivation concept. For instance, if a salesperson with an interest in self-development has the opportunity to realize this in his work, then they will have higher motivation (Elliot & Harackiewicz, 1994; Miao & Evans, 2012a). Intrinsic rewards link salespeople's individual psychological states with their tasks and become more critical than other factors (Mallin & Pullins, 2009). Intrinsic motivation is a persistent personal characteristic (Amabile, 1997) and may be revealed through specific conditions found within companies (Wiersma, 1992; Miao & Evans, 2014).

Salespeople remain in the middle of the relationship dynamic between their company and customers. Their roles are so important to the success of these relations, which is why their motivation is worth taking into account. With intrinsic motivation, salespeople focus on the tasks that make them feel satisfied (Amyx & Alford, 2013). Moreover, salespeople may seek to take on more responsibility and show more initiative (Miao & Evans, 2014). Due to the difficulty of sales tasks, it is unlikely that salespeople will become successful or deliver sales over the long-term without personal interest. Studies in sales management highlight that intrinsic motivation is key to sales performance (Weitz et al., 1986; Spiro & Weitz, 1990; Oliver & Anderson, 1994).

H₃: Authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's intrinsic motivation.

1.5 Working Hard

It is no surprise that being hard-working is an indispensable factor behind success in sales (Sujan, 1986; Brown & Peterson, 1994; Sujan et al., 1994; VandeWalle et al., 1999; Krishnan et al., 2002). In short, working hard can be defined as the individual efforts and the time spent by salespeople in their sales tasks compared to others (Sujan et al., 1988; Miao & Evans,

2012b). Hard-working salespeople do not give up when faced with failure or obstacles, but keep working (Sujan et al., 1994; Krishnan et al., 2002). Due to the nature of the sales function, salespeople are exposed to less supervision since they generally work out of the office. They spend copious amounts of time in the field with their customers. Hard-working salespeople manage their time more efficiently by planning their schedule in a smarter way. Previous research has observed a strong positive correlation between working hard and sales performance (Brown & Peterson, 1994; VandeWalle et al., 1999; Silver et al., 2006; Chakrabarti et al., 2013).

H₄: Authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's working hard.

2. Method

The variables of the research are presented in Figure 1. As seen in the model, authentic leadership is the independent variable, while salespeople's learning orientation, customer orientation, intrinsic motivation and working hard are the dependent variables.

Figure 1. Research Model

Data for the study were obtained from salespeople who live in Istanbul. In line with the convenience sampling approach, salespeople and sales supervisors were contacted directly. Furthermore, in order to maintain objectivity, only limited participation by those in the same companies was permitted. In the end, completed surveys from 364 salespeople from 115 companies were received. The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographics	%
Gender	
Male	79.8
Female	20.2
Education	
High School	15.2
Bachelor's	70.5
Master's	14.3
Age	
<26	4.2
26-32	40.5
33-39	37.8
>39	17.5
Period with Current Supervisor	
0-2 years	53.9
3-5 years	31.4
>5 years	14.7

Five-point Likert scales were used to measure the constructs. Authentic leadership was measured with The Authentic Leadership Questionnaire by Walumbwa et al. (2008). For copyright reasons, Mind Garden Ltd. was contacted in order to receive permission to use the scale. For learning orientation, seven items were adopted from Sujan et al. (1994). Customer orientation scale was formed by five items from Saxe and Weitz (1982). Intrinsic motivation was measured with three items from Anderson and Oliver (1987). Also three items were taken from Sujan et al. (1994) for working hard scale.

Validity and reliability of the scales were checked using confirmatory factor analysis. In the process, the PLS regression method was preferred. This method is reported as providing consistent results even in small sample sizes (Chin, 1998). The analysis was conducted with Smart PLS 3 software (Ringle et al., 2015). Items with low factor loadings were disregarded (Hair et al., 2011; Hair et al., 2014, p. 102). Finally, as shown in Appendix 1, all factor loadings were found to be over 0.60. The statistical significance of confirmatory factor analysis was tested by the bootstrap procedure with 1,000 samples (Hair et al., 2014, p. 134). According to the results, all items were statistically significant ($t > 2.57$, $p < 0.01$).

Convergent validity and discriminant validity were checked in accordance with the directions of Hair et al. (2014, p121). Convergent validity was assured by meeting the following conditions: (1) factor loadings of all items exceeded 0.60; (2) items loaded relevant constructs and withdrew from others; and, (3) as exhibited in Table 2, average variance extracted (AVE) was greater than 0.50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Similarly, discriminant validity was confirmed by observing that: (1) all items indicated the highest loadings in relevant factors, as stated in the cross loadings table in Appendix 2; and, (2) according to Fornell - Larcker (1981), the square root of the AVE values were higher than all the correlations with other factors, as presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Factor Correlations

No	Factor	Mean	SD	CR	Cr. α	AVE	\sqrt{AVE}	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Authentic Leadership	3.693	0.700	0.939	0.930	0.507	0.712	1.000								
2	Customer Orientation	4.100	0.557	0.835	0.740	0.559	0.748	0.358	1.000							
3	Working Hard	4.178	0.657	0.886	0.807	0.723	0.850	0.251	0.537	1.000						
4	Intrinsic Motivation	4.260	0.613	0.885	0.805	0.720	0.849	0.334	0.518	0.563	1.000					
5	Learning Orientation	4.297	0.572	0.877	0.827	0.588	0.767	0.251	0.390	0.501	0.526	1.000				
6	Balanced Processing	3.721	0.884	0.929	0.885	0.813	0.901	0.827	0.366	0.262	0.321	0.191	1.000			
7	Internalized Moral Perspective	3.634	0.788	0.885	0.826	0.658	0.811	0.794	0.180	0.160	0.180	0.226	0.483	1.000		
8	Relational Transparency	3.767	0.839	0.903	0.857	0.699	0.836	0.808	0.273	0.158	0.194	0.075	0.606	0.545	1.000	
9	Self-Awareness	3.658	0.874	0.935	0.906	0.781	0.884	0.889	0.353	0.244	0.383	0.312	0.678	0.640	0.565	1.000

N=376, SD: Standard Deviation, CR: Composite Reliability, Cr. α : Cronbach's alpha, AVE: Average Variance Extracted
Correlations are significant at 0.01 level.

Reliabilities were also checked using the same method (Hair et al., 2014, p. 101), which showed that scales were found to be reliable by ensuring that the composite reliability (CR) of all structures were over 0.70, while the Cronbach α values were also over 0.70.

3. Findings

PLS regression analysis was conducted in order to test the relationship between the variables and the hypothesis of the research. According to the analysis, the second order construct of authentic leadership was found to be valid and reliable as well as others. Authentic leadership was demonstrated as a second order construct that contains four sub-dimensions and the paths were drawn as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. PLS Analysis

According to the analysis, the second order construct of authentic leadership was found to be valid and reliable as well as others. As a result, it was observable that authentic leadership leads to significant positive effects upon learning orientation ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$; $t=8.84$; $R^2=0.07$), customer orientation ($\beta=0.358$; $p<0.01$; $t=6.02$; $R^2=0.13$), intrinsic motivation ($\beta=0.334$; $p<0.01$; $t=8.21$; $R^2=0.12$), and working hard ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$; $t=5.33$; $R^2=0.06$). Therefore the proposed hypothesis H_1 , H_2 , H_3 , and H_4 were accepted.

4. Conclusion

The results of the analysis indicate that authentic leadership behaviours of sales supervisors have positive effects on salespeople's learning orientation ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$). Learning orientation of salespeople is important for several reasons. Firstly, salespeople need to know not only the products of their company but also those of their competitors. They should closely follow market competition and be acquainted with alternative options that customers could choose. Secondly, they should be familiar with the customers' market and their position in it, as well as their customers' buying processes and the way that they use or consume products and services. As such, salespeople must demonstrate the capacity to learn. Moreover, salespeople often change their job or move to other divisions in the company. A learning orientation will help salespeople adapt to these new roles, products and customers (Dweck & Leggett, 1988; Ahearne et al., 2010), as well as improve their sales performance (Sujan et al., 1994; Kohli et al. 1998; Silver et al., 2006). The concept of authentic leadership also focuses on developing followers (Avolio et al., 2004). The results of this study demonstrate that a positive relationship exists between learning orientation and authentic leadership.

The results of the analysis also support the claim that authentic leadership has a significant effect upon customer orientation ($\beta=0.358$; $p<0.01$). Customer orientation is the application of the marketing concept in sales (Saxe & Weitz, 1982) and requires nurturing long-term relations with customers (Schwepker, 2003). Within customer orientation, the quality of the relationship is emphasized. The major challenge in achieving success in long-term relationships is cultivating trust. Moreover, customer orientation is also concerned with avoiding putting the customer under pressure and instead allowing them to make their own decision. Authentic leaders set high moral standards and also encourage salespeople to be honest and reliable. Supported by authentic leadership, salespeople will become braver in informing their customers of the advantages and disadvantages of their offers. They will not try to mislead their customers. Given that customer orientation is reported to have positive effects on customer satisfaction (Saxe & Weitz, 1982; Joshi & Randall, 2001), customer retention (Rozell et al., 2006), and sales performance (Franke & Park, 2006; Cross et al., 2007; Wachner et al., 2009), the effects of authentic leadership, then, makes appreciable sense.

Another finding from the analysis is that a positive relationship exists between authentic leadership and intrinsic motivation ($\beta=0.334$; $p<0.01$). Intrinsically motivated salespeople believe that their job is important and that they make a useful contribution. Unless they enjoy and respect the importance of their job, a salesperson should neither expect to be successful

nor to pursue a long-term career in sales. Due to the nature of this profession, customer complaints and other problems must be dealt with. Without intrinsic motivation, salespeople may 'give up' when faced with such challenges and, in turn, lose interest in their job. Authentic leadership from sales supervisors can make a difference in situations like this. By possessing a capacity for positive psychology, they keep their hope and optimism and demonstrate that they only act in accordance with what they believe in. Whenever salespeople see their leaders act in this way, they will consider them to be a role model. The result of this study is consistent with the authentic leadership theory, which suggests that authentic leadership has positive effects on the meaningfulness behind followers' activities (Avolio et al., 2004) and job satisfaction (Walumbwa et al., 2008). As Sujan (1986) and Weitz et al. (1986) stated, with increased intrinsic motivation, salespeople take more responsibilities and deliver higher levels of performance (Weitz et al., 1986; Spiro & Weitz, 1990; Oliver & Anderson, 1994).

The last finding concerns whether a positive relationship also exists between authentic leadership and salespeople's working hard ($\beta=0.251$; $p<0.01$). As Sujan (1986), Brown & Peterson (1994), Sujan et al. (1994), VandeWalle et al. (1999), and Krishnan et al. (2002) stated being hard-working is essential for sales. Avolio et al. (2004) stated that authentic leadership affects the behaviors and attitudes of the followers and Gardner et al. (2005) added that they will put more effort to work. The results of the study support this claim quantitatively. Working under authentic sales leaders, salespeople will feel increased meaningfulness behind their tasks and, in turn, work harder.

To sum up, it has been discovered that sales supervisors' authentic leadership has positive effects on salespeople's task-related outcomes. The biggest trap for sales supervisors is to continue thinking and acting like a salesperson after being promoted to a leadership role. A sales supervisor who believes that everything they did as a salesperson was right may lose their objectivity towards the development of their team. The pressure to meet targets may lead these supervisors to encourage their staff to focus on delivering their individual contribution at the risk of ignoring customer satisfaction. To this extent, the importance of authentic leadership emerges once more. Leaders who not only perform in order to satisfy their own goals but also take care of the people around them are needed in sales organizations. In the pursuit of individual goals, sales leaders should give sufficient consideration to their sales team as well as respect their values. By doing this, they should be able to create value by developing solutions that attract common interest from all stakeholders. Authentic sales leaders who do not sacrifice their personality nor their values, while also retaining high ethical and moral standards, ought to be able to connect short-term achievements to the long-term.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Confirmatory Factor Analysis Factor Loadings

No	Scale	Factor Loadings
	Customer Orientation	
2	I always present the customer with a realistic picture of what my firm's products can do.	0.7824
3	I spend much of my time listening to the customer talk about his/her firm's needs.	0.6637
4	I wait until I fully understand the customer's needs before making my sales presentation.	0.7884
5	I am always candid in discussions with my customers.	0.7487
	Intrinsic Motivation	
2	I sell because of the feeling of performing a useful service	0.8274
3	I obtain a sense of accomplishment from my work	0.8943
4	I feel a sense of personal growth and development in my work	0.8221
	Learning Orientation	
1	An important part of being a good salesperson is continually improving your sales skills	0.8070
2	It is important for me to learn from each selling experience I have	0.7128
5	It is worth spending a great deal of time learning new approaches for dealing with customers	0.7895
6	Learning how to be a better salesperson is of fundamental importance to me	0.7468
7	I put in a great deal of effort sometimes to learn something new	0.7734
	Working Hard	
1	I work long hours to meet my sales objectives.	0.7622
2	I do not give up easily when I encounter a customer who is difficult to sell.	0.8706
3	I work untiringly at selling a customer until I get an order.	0.9106

Confirmatory Factor Analysis Factor Loadings

No	Authentic Leadership Scale					Factor Loadings
	My leader;	F0	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	says exactly what he or she means.	0.6924	0.5535	0.5007	0.8419	0.4463
2	admits mistakes when they are made.	0.6384	0.4333	0.4078	0.8529	0.4485
3	encourages everyone to speak their mind.	0.6477	0.5099	0.3610	0.8102	0.4838
4	*	0.7189	0.5240	0.5416	0.8391	0.5073
5	*	0.6177	0.3743	0.8400	0.4617	0.4282
6	*	0.7289	0.4497	0.8549	0.5366	0.6028
8	*	0.5919	0.3129	0.7878	0.3738	0.5045
9	*	0.6223	0.4179	0.7577	0.3805	0.5276
10	*	0.7372	0.8736	0.4321	0.6085	0.5634
11	*	0.7102	0.9026	0.4262	0.4678	0.5805
12	*	0.7869	0.9275	0.4468	0.5595	0.6847
13	*	0.7436	0.5919	0.4788	0.5008	0.8384
14	*	0.8112	0.6399	0.6304	0.4673	0.9004
15	*	0.7955	0.5943	0.5762	0.5016	0.9042
16	*	0.7908	0.5710	0.5711	0.5282	0.8908
* : Hidden due to the copyright of Mind Garden Ltd. F0: Authentic Leadership (2 nd order) F1: Relational Transparency F2: Internalized Moral Perspective		F3: Balanced Processing F4: Self-Awareness				

Confirmatory Factor Analysis: Factor Loadings, Standard Deviation and t Statistics

	Factor Loading	Standard Deviation	t Statistics
al01 → relational transparency	0.8419	0.0163	51.5211
al01 → authentic leadership	0.6924	0.0314	22.0349
al02 → relational transparency	0.8529	0.0166	51.3569
al02 → authentic leadership	0.6384	0.0356	17.9318
al03 → relational transparency	0.8102	0.0210	38.5781
al03 → authentic leadership	0.6477	0.0376	17.2141
al04 → relational transparency	0.8391	0.0166	50.5791
al04 → authentic leadership	0.7189	0.0320	22.4989
al05 → internalized moral perspective	0.8400	0.0189	44.3927
al05 → authentic leadership	0.6177	0.0421	14.6719
al06 → internalized moral perspective	0.8549	0.0135	63.2705
al06 → authentic leadership	0.7289	0.0295	24.7021
al08 → internalized moral perspective	0.7878	0.0253	31.1872
al08 → authentic leadership	0.5919	0.0401	14.7646
al09 → internalized moral perspective	0.7577	0.0300	25.2457
al09 → authentic leadership	0.6223	0.0395	15.7714
al10 → balanced processing	0.8736	0.0137	63.7247
al10 → authentic leadership	0.7372	0.0262	28.1022
al11 → balanced processing	0.9026	0.0125	72.1954
al11 → authentic leadership	0.7102	0.0311	22.8316
al12 → balanced processing	0.9275	0.0080	115.7168
al12 → authentic leadership	0.7869	0.0229	34.3336
al13 → self-awareness	0.8384	0.0188	44.5694
al13 → authentic leadership	0.7436	0.0210	35.3985
al14 → self-awareness	0.9004	0.0126	71.2376
al14 → authentic leadership	0.8112	0.0196	41.3911
al15 → self-awareness	0.9042	0.0114	79.5101
al15 → authentic leadership	0.7955	0.0179	44.5272
al16 → self-awareness	0.8908	0.0128	69.6036
al16 → authentic leadership	0.7908	0.0207	38.1530
co02 → customer orientation	0.7824	0.0318	24.6100
co03 → customer orientation	0.6637	0.0591	11.2342
co04 → customer orientation	0.7884	0.0329	23.9341
co05 → customer orientation	0.7487	0.0392	19.1241
im02 → intrinsic motivation	0.8274	0.0329	25.1612
im03 → intrinsic motivation	0.8943	0.0198	45.2673
im04 → intrinsic motivation	0.8221	0.0383	21.4852
lo01 → learning orientation	0.8070	0.0388	20.8036
lo02 → learning orientation	0.7128	0.0738	9.6622
lo05 → learning orientation	0.7895	0.0343	23.0340
lo06 → learning orientation	0.7468	0.0487	15.3378
lo07 → learning orientation	0.7734	0.0353	21.9227
wh01 → working hard	0.7622	0.0391	19.5099
wh02 → working hard	0.8706	0.0265	32.8816
wh03 → working hard	0.9106	0.0177	51.5377

al: Authentic Leadership, co: Customer Orientation, im: Intrinsic Motivation, lo: Learning Orientation, wh: Working Hard

Appendix 2. Cross Loadings

Item	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
al01	0.6924	0.1936	0.0863	0.1180	0.0719	0.5535	0.5007	0.8419	0.4463
al02	0.6384	0.2084	0.0903	0.1571	-0.0285	0.4333	0.4078	0.8529	0.4485
al03	0.6477	0.2406	0.1486	0.1273	0.0096	0.5099	0.3610	0.8102	0.4838
al04	0.7189	0.2695	0.1995	0.2414	0.1825	0.5240	0.5416	0.8391	0.5073
al05	0.6177	0.0709	0.1175	0.0630	0.0952	0.3743	0.8400	0.4617	0.4282
al06	0.7289	0.1304	0.1707	0.1962	0.1692	0.4497	0.8549	0.5366	0.6028
al08	0.5919	0.2024	0.1885	0.1562	0.2316	0.3129	0.7878	0.3738	0.5045
al09	0.6223	0.1842	0.0403	0.1621	0.2429	0.4179	0.7577	0.3805	0.5276
al10	0.7372	0.3084	0.2230	0.2419	0.1290	0.8736	0.4321	0.6085	0.5634
al11	0.7102	0.3069	0.2652	0.3258	0.2263	0.9026	0.4262	0.4678	0.5805
al12	0.7869	0.3714	0.2229	0.3023	0.1646	0.9275	0.4468	0.5595	0.6847
al13	0.7436	0.2880	0.1844	0.2914	0.2256	0.5919	0.4788	0.5008	0.8384
al14	0.8112	0.3202	0.1875	0.3450	0.3322	0.6399	0.6304	0.4673	0.9004
al15	0.7955	0.3185	0.2647	0.3848	0.2864	0.5943	0.5762	0.5016	0.9042
al16	0.7908	0.3193	0.2247	0.3289	0.2541	0.5710	0.5711	0.5282	0.8908
co02	0.2835	0.7824	0.4294	0.4956	0.3395	0.3148	0.1484	0.1863	0.2805
co03	0.1890	0.6637	0.3942	0.3643	0.2135	0.2296	0.0932	0.0488	0.2348
co04	0.2656	0.7884	0.4483	0.4759	0.3086	0.2581	0.0843	0.2114	0.3004
co05	0.3082	0.7487	0.3497	0.2329	0.2864	0.2826	0.1922	0.3151	0.2402
im02	0.2986	0.4148	0.4799	0.8274	0.4205	0.3322	0.1562	0.1241	0.3512
im03	0.2874	0.4886	0.5323	0.8943	0.5023	0.2202	0.1796	0.1808	0.3425
im04	0.2618	0.4126	0.4138	0.8221	0.4147	0.2625	0.1204	0.1936	0.2746
lo01	0.2013	0.2573	0.3093	0.3452	0.8070	0.1429	0.2036	0.0160	0.2774
lo02	0.1065	0.4357	0.4228	0.4993	0.7128	0.1588	0.0341	-0.0081	0.1509
lo05	0.1968	0.1619	0.3510	0.3162	0.7895	0.0563	0.2273	0.0500	0.2845
lo06	0.2016	0.4258	0.4905	0.5472	0.7468	0.1885	0.1241	0.1319	0.2111
lo07	0.2175	0.2840	0.3770	0.3666	0.7734	0.1909	0.2151	0.0670	0.2376
wh01	0.1836	0.3642	0.7622	0.3766	0.3961	0.1784	0.1386	0.1276	0.1638
wh02	0.1992	0.4585	0.8706	0.5299	0.4352	0.2489	0.0968	0.1308	0.1817
wh03	0.2492	0.5302	0.9106	0.5185	0.4473	0.2378	0.1683	0.1446	0.2629
F1: Authentic Leadership F2: Customer Orientation F3: Working Hard F4: Intrinsic Motivation F5: Learning Orientation F6: Balanced Processing F7: Internalized Moral Perspective F8: Relational Transparency F9: Self-Awareness					al: Authentic Leadership co: Customer Orientation im: Intrinsic Motivation lo: Learning Orientation wh: Working Hard				

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